

A novel solvent accumulation solution for absorption CO₂ capture

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Introduction

To decarbonize industrial processes, many point-source CO₂ emitters are currently looking to carbon capture (CC) to reach their emission reduction goals. A common method involves scrubbing the CO₂-containing gas (flue gas, biogas, etc.) with a liquid *solvent* to absorb the CO₂ present in the gas mixture. Aqueous solutions with amines are common solvents, but others such as aqueous potassium carbonate are also applied in certain industries.

A general characteristic for solvent-based CO₂ capture is a high requirement for process heating, typically in the form of low-pressure steam, to release the CO₂ absorbed by the solvent. This heat input is known as *regeneration heat*. Sourcing the regeneration heat nearly always comes at a significant cost, particularly for power plant integrations where low-pressure steam is commonly sourced from the steam turbine, incurring a penalty on the electricity production. In many industries, sourcing the regeneration heat from within the plant is a difficult or impractical proposal. This can be remedied by using electrically driven high-temperature heat pumps to electrify the CC process, as all the regeneration heat supplied to the capture process can be recovered, albeit at lower temperature.

Regardless of the means for sourcing the regeneration heat, the *specific costs* per MWh of heat delivery often fluctuates significantly over time – This is particularly true for power grids with large penetration of intermittent renewables. At peak energy prices, moderating the regeneration heat input is an interesting cost-mitigation strategy. Listed below are examples of imperatives to vary the delivery of regeneration heat:

- Dynamic use of steam for other purposes, such as industrial processes, or generation of electricity, for which the sales price varies across the hours of the day (time scale: *hour*)
- Consumption of electricity for heat pumps, the cost of which varies over the course of a day (time scale: *hour*)
- Rapid changes in electricity production/consumption to deliver voltage/frequency support to the electrical grid (time scale: *seconds*)
- Changes in heat demand for regeneration due to changes in absorbed CO₂ (time scale: *minutes*)

A novel solution that addresses all the above, very real, examples is a *solvent accumulation system*. The solvent accumulator, described in subsequent sections, enables operation of *absorber* and *desorber* of the capture plant at different load points for a limited period.

Novelty and process description

A system for solvent accumulation is proposed in which lean and rich solvent may be stored for prolonged periods of time, as is shown in Figure 1. There are functionally two primary benefits from the solvent accumulation tank depending on the strategy for implementation:

1. **Strategy 1:** Nearly all energy delivery required to operate the CO₂ capture system may be avoided by using the solvent accumulation tank(s) to supply lean amine for the absorber and store the rich amine for later regeneration. The duration of the energy consumption reduction is limited only by the tank volume.
2. **Strategy 2:** In CO₂ capture plants with fluctuating feed gas flows, a smaller CO₂ capture system may be built by employing the solvent accumulator tank(s) to provide additional lean amine to provide additional lean amine to shave peaks of higher gas flows and store the excess rich amine for later regeneration.

If strategy 1 is selected, the stored lean solvent would be used for CO₂ absorption to either avoid or greatly reduce the consumption of steam and electricity in the CO₂ capture unit. This is achieved by sourcing lean solvent from storage to the absorber column and subsequently delivering the rich solvent to a rich solvent storage tank, thereby completely forgoing the desorber column. Saving regeneration steam during a specified duration ultimately means that the part of the capture plant contained by the grey area in Figure 1 will have to be scaled slightly larger to accommodate for extra capacity to make up the additional solvent regeneration necessary to offset accumulation of rich solvent.

If strategy 2 is implemented in CO₂ emitters with intermittent fluctuation peaks in the flow of feed gas, the solvent tanks are used to “peak shave” and capture additional CO₂ in periods with higher CO₂ flows. As an example, if the flow of CO₂ fluctuates between $\pm 25\%$ from the baseline, then the lean solvent volume in the storage tank(s) would be applied to capture additional CO₂ during periods with peak gas feed. In this way, only the absorber column needs to be scaled for the full peak gas feed while the rest of the capture plant can be scaled near baseline capacity dependent upon the frequency of gas feed fluctuations. This allows for much lower investment costs than for a plant with all components scaled for the peak gas feed.

Figure 1 - CO₂ capture systems with a double-tank solvent accumulation system

It should be noted that the solvent accumulation tank can also potentially be built as a single tank by employing the different densities of lean and rich amine in a stratified storage tank as is shown in Figure 2. Stratified storage tanks are well known from district heating systems where hot and cold water can be stored in the same tank by employing differences in density at different temperatures. This allows for increased flexibility for the district heating producer to plan production.

The primary benefit of choosing a stratified storage tank is that only half the tank volume is needed compared to a two-tank design. In the stratified tank, lean and rich solvent are stored with the rich

solvent at the bottom and lean solvent at the top with a boundary layer in between to separate the two solvent phases. In amine-based solvents, the density difference between lean and rich solvent can be upwards of 10 % - significantly more than the density difference found in stratified district heating accumulators – allowing for an efficient stratification.

Figure 2 - CO₂ capture system with a single stratified solvent accumulation tank

It should be noted that the stratified solvent accumulation system shown in Figure 2, will have a mixing boundary layer between the lean and rich solvent. The depth of this boundary layer and potential CO₂ diffusion across the mixing layer will dictate the efficiency of the single-tank storage solution.

A visual representation of applying strategy 1 to provide additional electricity production at peak electricity prices is shown in Figure 3. As electricity demand fluctuates daily, a corresponding increase in electricity prices is often observed. Typically, daily electricity demand follows that described with the duck curve, with peaks in demand observed in the mornings and evenings of the day due to power-intensive processes such as cooking, laundry etc. Oftentimes the peaks in electricity demand requires the use of expensive peak shaving power plants, causing the electricity price to increase. Thus, for an example case power plant with CC integrated, it can be beneficial to incorporate a solvent accumulation system to allow for extra electricity delivery at the peak prices. This is visualized by the green line in Figure 3, that may be seen to increase when electricity prices are high and decrease when electricity prices are low. Effectively this means that electricity production is shifted from periods with low electricity costs to periods with high electricity costs.

In Figure 4, the corresponding trend in the reboiler duty is seen for the example case. During the peak electricity prices, the reboiler duty decreases to zero to maximize the power delivery afforded by the reboiler steam instead expanding through the turbine, as seen in Figure 3. During hours with low electricity prices, where the reboiler steam consumption incurs little economic penalty, the reboiler duty is increased above nominal use to regenerate the additional rich solvent stored in the solvent accumulation system.

Figure 3 – Example case for power plant with CO₂ capture and a solvent accumulation system – showing relation of power delivery

Figure 4 – Example case for power plant with CO₂ capture and a solvent accumulation system – showing relation for reboiler duty

Introduction of one or two solvent accumulators adds CAPEX to the plant. For strategy 1, the implementation of a solvent accumulation tank further requires over-dimensioning of the solvent regeneration facilities to allow for regeneration of the accumulated rich solvent stored during periods of utilization. Regenerating more solvent also results in a higher flow of stripped CO₂ from the regeneration facility necessitating the over-dimensioning of CO₂ compression and conditioning systems. For strategy 2, the implementation of a solvent accumulation tank could potentially effectuate a reduction of the CC plant CAPEX by allowing most of the CC facility to be scaled below the peak gas feed.

Conclusion

A novel solution with a solvent accumulation system is proposed to optimize the performance of a solvent-based CO₂ capture system. The solvent accumulation system allows for flexible decoupled operation of the absorption and regeneration parts of the CO₂ capture system. For power plant integrations, the proposed solution allows for a temporary increase in the power delivery, through reductions in the reboiler duty. This additional power delivery may be strategically fitted for periods with high energy costs to maximize income. Additionally, for industrial plants with fluctuating gas feeds with variable amounts of CO₂, the proposed solution allows for a relatively lower CAPEX capture facility by utilizing the solvent accumulator in periods with peak gas feeds.